

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ACTIVITIES OF PREVENTION INSPECTORS WORKING WITH VICTIMS OF OFFENSES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13945351>

Annotation: The significance of this article lies in the fact that the concept of the activities of preventive inspectors working with victims of offenses, its essence and organization of work, as well as current problems and shortcomings in this area, are shown. In addition, opinions were put forward on the development of solutions to violations committed in the regions and the causes and conditions that allow them to be committed, documents to be formalized when they are committed, and other problems.

Keywords: crime, victimology, victim, antisocial behavior, prevention, public control, migration.

It is known that the complexity and multifaceted nature of the activities of law enforcement officers in the prevention of offenses, the breadth and diversity of their powers and tasks, and their struggle for human life and destiny in various spheres of public life require special responsibility.

Ensuring the safety and well-being of another person, as well as a thorough study of the types of victims of violations, requires timely implementation of necessary measures to eliminate victimological causes and conditions.

An analysis of the results of legal reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of ensuring law and order, protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens shows that timely detection and detection of any violation, and the punishment of perpetrators in accordance with the law play an important role in preventing offenses.

Therefore, it is noteworthy that today, preventive inspectors, in cooperation with citizens' self-government bodies and public organizations, are implementing practical measures to improve the effectiveness of crime prevention, which serves to strengthen the legal foundations of victimological prevention activities in working with victims.

In order to ensure the implementation of these measures, a number of positive actions have been taken and are being implemented by prevention inspectors. Of course, it is important to emphasize the importance of proper

organization of victimological crime prevention in the activities of prevention inspectors in achieving such successes.

At the same time, the causes and conditions that have arisen in the practice of preventing violations of the law show that much work needs to be done to properly organize and increase the effectiveness of the activities of prevention inspectors in the implementation of victimological prevention.

In our view, taking into account the specifics of organizing victimological crime prevention by the prevention inspector plays a significant role in enhancing the effectiveness of crime prevention activities. From a victimological perspective, crime prevention measures should be implemented not against individuals who may commit crimes, but against individuals who may be victims of crimes, and should be aimed at eliminating aspects that contribute to the formation of such a predisposition.

This situation in legal literature is divided into economic, political, and ideological types according to the content of crime prevention measures and various types of measures for the implementation of crime prevention activities.

It should be noted that all types of crime prevention activities are interconnected and complement each other. In the fight against offenses, one should not forget their goals and objectives. When organizing victimological crime prevention, it is advisable to study the subjects of crime prevention by dividing them into three groups.

The first group consists of entities that take measures to organize, lead, and coordinate the activities of all entities in the field of crime prevention.

The second group includes subjects whose primary task is to implement direct measures to prevent offenses.

The third group includes subjects directly involved in the prevention of individual offenses at the initial stage. When organizing victimological crime prevention, division into such groups is considered conditional.

In our view, a person must be spiritually educated in order to become a victim of a crime as a result of unexpected circumstances.

Educational and labor communities are also the main environment for the formation of a person as an individual. Especially educational institutions play an important role in the formation of minors as individuals. Because they are not limited to the acquisition of knowledge in the educational institution, but are formed under the influence of relationships within it.

All of this is based on upbringing. We have emphasized that the origin of various offenses largely depends on the victim's own actions. For example, if a

young girl tries to make casual acquaintances, drinks alcohol with them, tries to attract people's attention, it is natural that she becomes a victim of a crime, or if the victim of the crime leaves a valuable item or money unattended due to excessive trustworthiness, simplicity, and carelessness of her character, theft may occur spontaneously.

Furthermore, if a person who consumes alcohol in excess and insults others, it is not unlikely that he will be the initiator of the scandal and, as a result, become a victim of offenses with bodily injuries. The organization of the victimological prevention of offenses by the prevention inspector is also characterized by these aspects. Of course, conducting propaganda and explanatory work with individuals who, as a result of their actions, may become victims of various offenses, in harmony with national values, enriching the religious and secular world of the individual can be an important tool in preventing victimological factors. Regarding the activities of prevention inspectors in organizing victimological prevention of victims of offenses, it should be remembered that the above-mentioned actions of victims of offenses are considered cases that lead to the commission of traffic accidents, bodily harm, theft, hooliganism, etc.

Therefore, in our view, the implementation of victimological crime prevention activities by the prevention inspector should be based on an appropriate classification of such prevention, as a differentiated approach to victims of crime plays a key role in the implementation of victimological prevention.

Based on this, it can be said that in the prevention of victims of offenses, first and foremost, a person's self-education means being able to refrain from a negative direction in their actions.

Here we are talking about the need for each person to be able to think about their actions independently and manage them. Furthermore, as a result of any managerial influence, including preventive ones, the controlled subsystem has its own interests, interests, and goals, and acts based on them.

In the activities of prevention inspectors working with victims of crime, the organization of victimological prevention can be carried out in various directions, depending on the level of crime prevention and the content of current and future tasks. For example, identifying violations in a specific area where a prevention inspector serves;

- implementation of large-scale measures in cooperation with local government bodies, public organizations to eliminate conditions that contribute to victimological factors;

- establishing regular cooperation with the leadership of mahallas, schools, colleges, and universities in the prevention of offenses;

"to carry out explanatory work on the responsibility of observing the established rules of morality, etc.

In our view, a crucial feature of the organization of work by a prevention inspector with victims of crime is that, along with mastering the experience of developed countries in crime prevention, special attention should be paid to our national values, based on the national mentality of our country.

